

Attempt to Account Quantitatively for the Variation of Specific Conductivity of Cetyltrimethylammoniumbromide and Cetylpyridiniumbromide with Dilution On Colloidal Electrolytes.

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It has been shown that the variation of specific conductivity, X_c , over a wide range of stoichiometric concentration, C , of the solutions of Cetylpyridinium bromide and Cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide can be accounted for by the following equation

$$X_c - X_o = X_m \frac{(C - C_o)}{K + (C - C_o)} [1 + \beta(C - C_a)]$$

where C_o represents the c.m.c., X_o the corresponding specific conductivity, X_m , K , and β and constants and C_a the stoichiometric concentration at which the diffuse electrical double layers of the micelles begin to overlap.

It has also been shown that the specific surface conductance, χ , of the micelles can be found if X_m and the radius, r , is known. In the case of (CPB) the value of χ has been found to be 1.56×10^{-9} .

In a previous paper¹ it has been shown that the variation, with dilution, of osmotic pressure, specific conductivity and counter ion activity of the sols of Congo red and Cetyl-sulphonic acid can be accounted for by certain equations derived on the basis of the following assumptions.

(I) Each micelle or colloidal particle is surrounded by an electrical double layer made up of two parts, the fixed Stern²-Mukherjee³ layer and the diffuse double layer (i.e., the Gouy-Chapman layer).

(II) The counter ions cannot go beyond the boundary of the diffuse double layer of the micelle to which they belong. When a micelle moves sufficiently close to the osmometer membrane or to the reversible electrode placed in the sol, so that the diffuse double layer is in contact with the membrane or the electrode, then only the counter ions present in this portion of the double layer can register their activity on the membrane or the electrode.

(III) Starting from the outermost boundary of the diffuse double layer, the activity of the counter ions increases according to the Boltzmann distribution law as the surface of the micelle or the particle is approached.

(IV) In the case of a micellar or association colloid, it is assumed that if C_o represents the c.m.c. then the number of micelles, x , in unit volume, at a stoichiometric concentration C of the micelle forming electrolyte, is equal to $K(C - C_o)$, where K is a proportionality constant

and $C \gg C_0$. For the sake of simplicity it is also assumed that the micelles are all of the same size.

On the basis of the aforesaid assumptions the equation derived for the variation of specific conductivity with dilution of association colloids, when their concentration is so high that the diffuse double layers surrounding the micelles overlap, is written as follows:

$$X_c - X_0 = X_m \frac{(C - C_0)}{K + (C - C_0)} [1 + \beta(C - C_a)] \quad \dots (1)$$

where X_c and X_0 are the specific conductivities of the micelle forming electrolyte at the concentrations C and C_0 respectively, C_0 being the c.m.c. X_m is a constant representing the specific conductivity at the plane within the diffuse double layer in contact with the electrodes of the conductivity cell. K and β are constants and C_a represents the stoichiometric concentration of the micelle forming electrolyte at which the diffuse double layers of the micelles begin to overlap.

When C is equal to or lower than C_a the term involving β in equation (1) disappears and then it assumes the simple form

$$X_c - X_0 = X_m \frac{(C - C_0)}{K + (C - C_0)} \quad \dots (1a)$$

Verification of the equations (1) and (1a): In this paper it is proposed to test the validity of the equations (1) and (1a) using the data of Hartley, Collie and Samis⁴ on the equivalent conductivities of cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) and cetylpyridinium bromide (CPB).

The aforesaid authors have measured the conductivity and transport number of (CTAB) and (CPB) over a wide range of concentration and have suggested 0.0009 N and 0.00075 N respectively as the probable values of their c.m.c.

From the concentration and equivalent conductivity data of Hartley *et al.*⁴, the corresponding specific conductivities have been calculated and these are recorded in the Tables 1 and 2.

In the equations (1) and (1a) the value of C_0 for (CPB) has been taken as 0.0008 N and that for (CTAB) equal to 0.00095 N . It appears from the data of Hartley *et al.*⁴ that the equivalent conductivities at infinite dilution of (CPB) and (CTAB) are 118 and 120 respectively at 35°. Therefore, the values of X_0 for (CPB) and (CTAB) have been taken as 9.4×10^{-5} (i.e., 0.118×0.0008) and 11.4×10^{-5} (i.e., 0.120×0.00095) recip. ohms respectively. The value of C_a for both the long chain electrolytes has been taken as 0.08 N for the following reasons.

Since the values of C_0 (i.e., c.m.c.) of (CPB) and (CTAB) are less than $1 \times 10^{-3} N$ the thickness of the diffuse double layer surrounding a micelle of each of them will be slightly greater than 10^{-6} cm. according to the theory of Verwey and Overbeek⁵. If it be assumed that on an average as many as 40 long chain ions associate to form a micelle then at 0.08 N

the distance between the centers of the neighbouring micelles will be about 0.94×10^{-6} cm.* Hence at a concentration of the long chain electrolytes somewhat lower than $0.08 N$ the diffuse double layers of the micelles should begin to overlap.

TABLE 1

(CTAB)

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 T = 35^\circ; & X_m = 0.021 \text{ recip. ohms.}; & K = 0.69 \\
 C_0 = 0.00095 N & & \beta = 1.3 \\
 X_0 = 11.4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ recip. ohms.} & & C_a = 0.08 N
 \end{array}$$

<i>C</i> in gram equiv/L.	Specific conductivity $\times 10^5$ in recip. ohms		<i>C</i> in gram equiv/L.	Specific conductivity $\times 10^5$ in recip. ohms	
	Observed	Calculated		Observed	Calculated
0.00868	35.2	34.7	0.0692	200.7	200.4
0.0114	43.0	42.7	0.173	489.6	481.3
0.0247	79.0	81.2	0.278	750.6	767.7
0.0534	157.5	159.7	0.409	1116.6	1125.8
0.0648	189.2	189.3	0.421	1166.2	1158.2

TABLE 2

(CPB.)

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 T = 35^\circ; & X_m = 0.018 \text{ recip. ohms.} & K = 0.56 \\
 C_0 = 0.0008 N & & \beta = 1.3 \\
 X_0 = 9.4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ recip. ohms.} & & C_a = 0.08 N
 \end{array}$$

<i>C</i> in gram equiv/L.	Specific conductivity $\times 10^5$ in recip. ohms.		<i>C</i> in gram equiv/L.	Specific conductivity $\times 10^5$ in recip. ohms.	
	Observed	Calculated		Observed	Calculated
0.00156	11.7	11.8	0.0074	30.7	30.4
0.00247	14.9	14.8	0.0138	49.4	50.2
0.00345	18.2	17.9	0.0355	110.1	114.4
0.00499	23.2	22.8	0.1099	319.8	314.4

DISCUSSION

It may be pointed out that X_m in the equations (1) and (1a) involves the average values of (1) the area $\bar{A}$ of the double layer of a micelle in contact with the electrodes and (2) also the average values of the velocities of a counter ion and a micelle. Therefore, owing to fluctuation from these averages, difference is likely to occur between the observed and the calculated values of specific conductivity.

* For values of C higher than C_a , the c.m.c. should diminish progressively and so the values of X_0 should diminish proportionately. At this stage X_0 is less than 3% of X_c and hence the effect is masked.

It is also to be noted that when the sol is diluted with water, the concentration of the long chain ions falls below the equilibrium value (i.e., the c.m.c.) and so there occurs dissolution of the micelles to some extent to restore equilibrium. If the attainment of this equilibrium requires some time and if the specific conductivity is measured before the system attains equilibrium then the observed value should differ from that calculated.

In spite of these disturbing factors, it will be noticed from the data recorded in the tables 1 and 2 that the agreement between the observed and the calculated values of the specific conductivity is satisfactory in most of the cases.

It may be mentioned that for dilute sols, the specific surface conductance, χ , of the micelles of (CPB.) and (CTAB) can be connected with their respective X_m by the following equation:

$$4\pi r^2 \chi = \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 X_m \quad \dots (2)$$

where, r represents the radius of a micelle.

For (CPB), Hartley and Runnicles⁶ have found, r , from diffusion measurements, to be about 26×10^{-8} cm. Therefore, for the micelles of (CPB)

$$\chi = X_m \frac{r}{3} = \frac{1.8 \times 10^{-2} \times 26 \times 10^{-8}}{3} = 1.56 \times 10^{-9}$$

This value of χ for (CPB) is of the same order of magnitude as that of Jena glass found by Rutgers and Smet.⁷

REFERENCES

1. B. N. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972
2. O. Stern, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1924, **30**, 508.
3. J. N. Mukherjee, *Trans. Faraday. Soc.*, 1920-21, **16**, 103.
4. A. S. Hartley, B. Collie, and C. S. Samis, *Trans. Faraday. Soc.*, 1936, **32**, 795.
5. E. J. W. Verwey and J. Th. G. Overbeek, *Theory of the Stability of Lyophobic Colloids*, Elsevier Publishing Company, Inc., Amsterdam, 1948, p. 29.
6. G. S. Hartley and D. F. Runnicles, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1938, **168A**, 420.
7. A. J. Rutgers and M. De Smet, *Trans. Faraday. Soc.*, 1945, **41**, 758.